

Academic Dishonesty in Islamic Primary Schools

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ABSTRACT: This research aimed to find out the forms and factors of academic dishonesty during the time of doing a task or test on Islamic Primary School Students in central Java, Indonesia. There were 7 informants in this research consisting of 4 primary informants that involved students from fourth, fifth, and sixth grades, and 3 secondary informants that involved homeroom teachers of the primary informants. This was qualitative research with a case study approach whose data were collected using interviews. The results showed that the forms of students' academic dishonesty included copying the answers, cheating, having their homework done by someone else, asking for and giving the answers, cooperating in cheating, correcting answers, bringing some notes, and lying about doing the assignments. Meanwhile, the factors that caused students to commit those dishonesties were low self-confidence, low internal motivation, gender, low control, unpreparedness for the test, conformity, and the ease of technology.

KEYWORDS: Academic Dishonesty; Students; Primary School; Islamic school; Cheating

I. INTRODUCTION

Education is an obligation for everyone, with the aim of none other than to add insight. Education can change humans from ignorance, the higher the level of education of a person, the wider the knowledge that can be obtained. To reach this level of education, humans must have integrity, professionalism, and creativity that are honed in the world of education (Wicaksono, 2017).

The implementation of education in Indonesia refers to the rules or regulations that have been made by the government, these regulations are stated in Law No. 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System which states that:

"National education functions in developing abilities and shaping dignified national character and civilization in order to educate the nation's life, aiming at developing the potential of students to become human beings who believe and fear only God Almighty, noble, healthy, knowledgeable, capable, creative, independent, and become democratic and responsible citizens".

Based on these objectives, the substance of educational goals is more on character education. It is also emphasized that education according to the Big Indonesian Dictionary is the process of changing the attitudes and behaviour of a person or group of people in an effort to mature humans through teaching and training efforts. According to Law no. 20 of 2003 article 3 education is a conscious and planned effort to create an atmosphere of learning and the learning process so that students actively develop their potential to have spiritual strength in religion, self-control, personality, intelligence, noble character, and skills needed by themselves, society, nation and state. Meanwhile, according to Horne (Raharjo, 2010), it is a continuous (eternal) process of higher adjustment for human beings who have developed physically and mentally, who are free and aware of God, as manifested in the intellectual environment. Emotional and humanitarian from humans.

From some of these definitions, the understanding is obtained that education is an effort to change one's attitude consciously continuously in order to develop the potential in one goal. The goals achieved are listed in Law No. 20 of 2003 article 3, one of which is noble morals. Noble morals according to Raharjo, (2010) are traits that are imprinted in the soul, from which deeds are born easily without thinking and pondering first, one of these noble morals is honesty.

Honesty is the attitude and behaviour in acting in real and what it is, not lying, not making up, not adding to, and not reducing nor hiding information (Astrini, 2015). Honesty is very much needed in this aspect of life. An honest attitude is an attitude that is instilled and applied in everyday life because an honest attitude is a good and praiseworthy attitude. The application of honest character can be started from an early age in the family, such as if you are guilty you have to admit your mistakes, between words

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and actions must be the same, tell something to your parents and the community, hold and carry out the mandate well (Chairilisyah, 2016)

In the world of education, the value of honesty needs to be developed to produce resources that can uphold the values of honesty. Educators have an important role in building the character, personality and intellectuality of students (Emosda, 2011). So that educators are one of the factors that determine the success of the application of the concept of honesty. An honest character that can be instilled in students according to (Susanti et al., 2020) can be done through modelling, spontaneous activities when the teacher finds out about good and bad students, exemplary stories or stories, conditioning, and routine activities.

However, this application is not easy. In fact, the application of honest character has not been maximally realized because there are still many values of honesty that are violated. As the results of (Herdian, (2017) states that academic dishonesty occurs starting from elementary school to college. Sari, (2015) examined academic dishonesty in junior high school students, saying that several factors of academic dishonesty in junior high school students were due to pressure to get high grades and the desire to avoid failure.

The education system in Indonesia still uses test scores or learning evaluations which cause people to see the success of learning achievement is only reflected in the achievement of learning outcomes, not in the process. This view creates pressure on students to get high scores. The pressure felt makes students more value-oriented rather than acquiring knowledge, students think that exams are a tool to show achievement not a monitoring tool in the learning process. This is the reason for the emergence of cheating which is an indicator of academic dishonesty behaviour in students from elementary, middle, upper and even tertiary levels (Kusumastuti, 2015).

The term dishonesty in the scope of education can be referred to as academic dishonesty or academic dishonesty. Academic dishonesty is an act or behaviour of a person by borrowing or copying assignments from others, copying assignments from others, copying answers during exams, and obtaining assignments or exam questions from the previous semester. Academic dishonesty can be defined as any treatment or action that involves dishonesty in academics as well as imitating, buying assignments, copying, and printing without the truth of the work of others (Latisha Asmaak & Surina, 2008).

Academic dishonesty according to Moeck, (2002) is that academic dishonesty is the misuse of academic material by destroying or changing parts of the content. Academic dishonesty according to Kibler (W. L. Kibler, 1993) is a form of cheating and plagiarism that involves students in illegally giving or receiving assistance in exams or receiving awards for work they do not do. Based on the description above, it can be concluded that academic dishonesty is an act of misusing material and violating the norms or rules that have been set in school, acting dishonestly or fraudulently by using various means for personal gain.

Academic dishonesty is a unique reckless behaviour that occurs in students and is associated with cheating on homework and plagiarism on academic assignments (Korn & Davidovitch, 2016). The deceptive act of fraudulent means is that students send the same paper to another class without permission and collaborate with others on assignments assigned as individual work. (Pedhazur & Aviele, 2001).

Some forms of academic dishonesty include asking for answers, asking for the essence of answers, looking at answers (without being noticed by friends), carrying cheats and searching for answers on the internet. The academic dishonesty factor is caused by the questions that come out during the exam are not studied or are not in accordance with what was learned while studying, do not know the answers, do not understand the material presented during lectures and learning is not optimal (Herdian & Lestari, 2018)

Based on the above background, the researcher is interested in further examining academic dishonesty in Islamic elementary school students, because elementary schools with a religious background can be a source of moral development and are positively related to morality and religiosity, primary schools are in a strategic environment in cultivation. Character, as an initial level that teaches the values of honesty to students and from habituation can become a habit towards the next level. The focus of this research is What Forms of Academic Dishonesty in Islamic Elementary School Students? And What Are the Causes of Academic Dishonesty in Islamic Elementary School Students?

II. METHOD

This study uses a qualitative method with a case study approach because this research will develop an in-depth analysis of how the forms and factors of academic dishonesty of students in Islamic elementary schools, Central Java, Indonesia. The researcher will limit the research to one or more variables, thus there needs to be a focus, namely the subject matter that is still general. In this study, the focus of the problem is the Forms of Academic Dishonesty in Islamic Elementary School Students and the Causes of Academic Dishonesty in Islamic Elementary School Students.

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The informants of this study consisted of primary informants and secondary informants. There are 4 primary informants consisting of grade 4 and class 6 each with 1 student, grade 5 with 2 students. Meanwhile, the secondary informants were student teachers, amounting to 3 informants. This is more clearly shown in table 1. Research participants.

In this study, the interview method used was semi-structured interviews, namely the interview process that had been prepared or compiled interview guidelines to find out data about the form and factors that influence academic dishonesty.

In this study, the interview method used was semi-structured interviews, namely, the interview process that had been prepared or the interview guidelines were compiled to find out data about the form and factors that influence academic dishonesty. Data analysis uses interactive analysis through several steps including data collection, data reduction, data presentation and drawing conclusions or verification.

Table 1. Research participants

No	Participant	Status	Note
1	Participant 1	Primer	Grade 4
2	Participant 2	Primer	Grade 5
3	Participant 3	Primer	Grade 5
4	Participant 4	Primer	Grade 6
5	Participant 5	Sekunder	Teacher
6	Participant 6	Sekunder	Teacher
7	Participant 7	Sekunder	Teacher

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

All paragraphs must be indented. All paragraphs must be justified, i.e. both left-justified and right-justified.

A. Form of academic dishonesty

Participant 1 commits dishonesty by copying a friend's answer by looking at the answers that friends have worked on and the answers are sent via WhatsApp. When participants have difficulty, participants see a friend's answer without the friend's knowledge. In addition, Participant 1 commits academic dishonesty by asking friends for answers when tests are difficult.

Participant 2 commits academic dishonesty by way of homework being done by others on craft assignments, cheating on friends during tests, working with friends, bringing cheats during tests by writing a cheat sheet on a drink bottle. Replace then justify with the correct answer when matching the test on short questions, if the length or description is only one or two questions.

Participant 3 commits academic dishonesty by copying a friend's work, seeing a friend's answer with the friend's permission, asking for help from parents who carry out homework, asking for answers from friends during tests. Cheating on daily assignments, collaborating with friends on almost all lessons except for the subject participant 3 likes, namely mathematics and improving answers when they are matched by replacing them with correct or corrected answers.

Participant 4 commits academic dishonesty by doing assignments with friends or collaborating. Copying a friend's work for doing it slowly in maths lessons, asking friends to help answer questions in tests, giving help by giving answers to friends.

"Yes, ask what answer via WhatsApp, the answer on what page, if a friend has done it I see it" participant 1

"I once put a cheat sheet on a bottle using a bottle" participant 2.

"Yes, look at my friend's answer, for a good friend I will see" Participant 3

"Yes, but my friends work fast, so I see what my friends have worked on" Participant 4

Secondary informants also said the same thing about forms of academic dishonesty in their students. Participant 5 said that academic dishonesty among students included homework done by other people because the work was neat, not like the work of children of his age, cooperating with friends by cheating while working and replacing then justifying answers on the grounds of incorrect writing. Participant 6 also explained that academic dishonesty was carried out in the form of saying that copying a friend's answer through a WhatsApp picture with an answer that his friend had done and immediately worked on it when he arrived at school. Furthermore, the secondary information, Participant 7, said a form of academic dishonesty, namely by asking for answers from friends on subjects who could not, giving answers to friends except in mathematics. Because in certain lessons not mastered "It is not students-made, because the work is neat and good" Participants 5

"At that time, he said that yesterday I saw the answer from the friend next to me, the problem was that he was tired of over sleeping" Participant 6

"Asked his friend even though I saw it was only math lessons he asked a friend" Participant 7

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Based on the findings of this study, it can be seen that academic dishonesty consists of several forms including copying answers, looking at answers, homework being done by others, asking for answers, giving answers, receiving answers, cheating, collaborating, confirming answers, carrying cheats and lying about assignments.

The form of academic dishonesty committed by Participant 1 is receiving answers, reinforced by Kibler's opinion (Kibler, 1993) which states that academic dishonesty is a form of cheating and plagiarism that involves students giving or receiving answers. In Ungusari, (2015) states that one form of dishonest behaviour is asking for answers. Participant 2 commits academic dishonesty by bringing cheats reinforced by the results of research from Arinda, (2015) which states that carrying cheats during exams is a form of academic dishonesty.

The form of academic dishonesty in the form of copying the answers made by Participant 1, Participant 3 and Participant 4 is reinforced by Colby's opinion (Fadlilah & Aisyah, 2017) that one indicator of academic dishonesty is copying other people's answers during exams. Participant 1 sees answers when in difficult situations, According to Sagoro, (2013) one of the actions of academic cheating is glancing at or seeing friends' answers. In Participant 2, the form of academic dishonesty that is carried out is by collaborating during tests and Participant 3 who lies about doing assignments, this opinion is in line with Lambert's opinion (Fadlilah & Aisyah, 2017) that another indicator of academic dishonesty is helping others to cheat. By cooperating during tests and copying assignments claiming to be their own work. Forms of academic dishonesty such as cheating in collaboration or asking for help were carried out by Participant 4, Participant 3 and Participant 2, reinforced by research results from Lestari & Asyanti (Herdian & Wulandari, 2018) that forms of academic dishonesty include asking for answers, copying and cheating.

B. The academic dishonesty factor

Participant 1 has low self-confidence because he thinks he cannot do it and if he sees a friend's work it is more true. Based on the information submitted by Participant 1, the factors behind committing academic dishonesty are utilizing the convenience of technology such as using WhatsApp to get answers from friends. Participant 1 follows his friend to commit academic dishonesty, besides that the background factor is conformity, namely a sense of wanting to follow something that other people do. Participant 2 when tests will commit academic dishonesty when supervision is low, such as when teachers are not paying attention to their students. Participant 3 has low self-confidence in Javanese language lessons because according to him it is difficult and does not understand because at home / everyday language uses a different language. Participant 3 imitates friends who commit academic dishonesty, low internal motivation factors, namely laziness to do assignments, inadequate preparation in learning so that when working on the questions they experience difficulties. Participant 4 has low self-confidence because he thinks that during certain lessons Participant 4 does it slowly unlike other friends who are fast and correct.

"Yes, I ever asked via WhatsApp, what's the answer, what is the answer on what page, Grandma have you, I see" Participant 1

"When the teacher uses a cell phone, but when I cheat, it's sometimes said" Participant 2

"Javanese language is difficult, the Javanese script does not understand the language at home using a different language" Participant 3

"Because my friend is working on it quickly and then the answer is correct, because sometimes I'm wrong" participant 4

According to Nursalam et al., (2016) who said that the factors that cause students to commit academic dishonesty are not confident with their own work or low self-confidence as happened to Participant 1, Participant 3 and Participant 4. In Participant 1 and Participant 3 the underlying factor is conformity, namely following friends who commit academic dishonesty, this is reinforced in the opinion of (Lestari & Asyanti, 2015) that dishonesty occurs when students watch their friends cheating. The convenience factor in technology is a factor causing participant 1 to commit academic dishonesty, reinforced by research according to Harris (Mustapha et al., 2017) the ease of technology factor is the strongest factor that academic dishonesty occurs. Participant factor 2 commits academic dishonesty when supervision is low, according to research by Ungusari, (2015) that in situations where students have exams and have difficulty working, then see friends who are cheating on each other when supervision is low, more students behave dishonestly. Due to the influence of the environment, namely friends who are cheating on each other and lax supervision so that when this situation occurs students will take advantage of the opportunity to be dishonest. Participant 3 in conducting academic dishonesty is based on the factor of unpreparedness in facing exams because there has been no prior preparation, this can be strengthened by Fitriyani's opinion (Nugroho, 2015) one of the factors causing academic dishonesty is mastery of the material besides the factor, namely exam unpreparedness.

IV. COCLUSIONS

Of the four participants studied, there were forms of academic dishonesty carried out by students, namely copying answers, seeing answers, homework being done by others, asking for answers, giving answers, receiving answers, cheating, collaborating,

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confirming answers, bringing cheats and lying about doing assignments . The factors of academic dishonesty from the four informants were low self-esteem, low internal motivation, gender, low supervision, unpreparedness to take exams, conformity and ease of technology.

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